

Study of Perceived Organizational Support and Work Engagement on Job Satisfaction

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to analyse among Job Satisfaction, especially problems regarding the effect of Perceived Organizational Support and Work Engagement on Job Satisfaction. From the data collection activities, 96 respondents were obtained. Data analysis was carried out with the help of the SPSS version 26 program, the data testing technique in this study included multiple linear regression test, coefficient of determination test, t test (partial test), and F test (simultaneous test). The results showed that partially Perceived Organizational Support had a positive effect on Job Satisfaction. This is indicated by t-count higher than t-table (21,525 and 1,985), and Work Engagement has a positive effect on Job Satisfaction. This is indicated by t-count higher than t-table (13,817 and 1,985), the regression significant value of 0.000 up to 0.050. And simultaneously, Perceived Organizational Support and Work Engagement have a positive effect on Job Satisfaction, where F-count is higher than F-table (308,577 and 3.09). Result of multiple regression equation value $Y = 8.104 + 0.551 X_1 + 0.271 X_2$.

INTRODUCTION

Employee job satisfaction is not only an inspiration from personal mental aspects, but also related to other aspects such as interactions in the work environment and social benefits from work produced by individuals/employees. Generally, job satisfaction is often associated with employee turnover. This tends to be caused if an individual/employee is satisfied with his job then he will stay in the organization. Conversely, individuals/employees who are dissatisfied with their jobs will choose to resign from their workplace. In the Tangerang-Banten area, the company PT SBB OPPO Manufacturing experienced a decline in performance allegedly due to employee turnover. In general, employees leave because there is no recognition of the existence of their personality through a work contract. In addition, no awards have been given, the issue of increasing career paths has not been regulated and management's attention to employee welfare has not been regulated.

In addition, rewards and wages for the work done are often the main thing in fulfilling job satisfaction. Regarding compensation, the Government of Indonesia has regulated it in PP no.36 year 2021 concerning Wages (Kemenkumham, 2021). If the desires and needs of an employee are met with appropriate rewards for their work, then employee satisfaction will increase. Individuals/employees who get satisfaction at work will be motivated to increase their work productivity. Because satisfaction will make someone feel comfortable and flexible in optimizing the role and performance of these employees. The higher the assessment of activities felt in accordance with individual wishes, the higher the satisfaction with these activities (Azhari et al., 2021).

The decline in employee Job Satisfaction at PT SBB OPPO Manufacturing can be monitored from the low work discipline, decreased enthusiasm for work and a reflection of employee attitudes that seem outside of proper professional manners. From some information it is stated that this condition occurs because work situations so far only involve work conditions and behaviour but do not involve emotional conditions.

Table 1. Job Satisfaction Factors at PT SBB OPPO Manufacturing

Job Satisfaction Factors	Percentage	Remarks
Work Facilities	60%	Not Fulfilled
Workload	44%	Not appropriate
Rewards and wages	53%	Not Fulfilled
Employee relationship	71%	Un-supporting
Supporting infrastructure	63%	Inadequate
Work environment	48%	Un-supporting

Figure 1. Condition of Job Satisfaction at PT SBB OPPO Manufacturing

As a whole, most employees feel that their social presence in the company is not appreciated and they have not felt full support from their superiors. From this description it is suspected that there is a relationship between job satisfaction and Perceived Organizational Support and Work Engagement.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Human Resource (HR)

HR has an important role in a company/organization. Usually, what is done by human resource managers describes how the activation of human resource management within environment. Human resources is a process that includes evaluating human resource needs, getting people to meet those needs, and optimizing the utilization of these important resources by providing appropriate incentives and assignments, to suit the needs and goals of the organization in which resources human power exists (Burhanudin, 2021).

In a review of management science by taking a psychological approach, HR does not only discuss technical or non-technical Job Achievements. HR management is considered as an inseparable part of management in general where it has a close relationship between superiors and subordinates and colleagues. In its development, HR plays a more humane role where its existence is returned to its nature as a creature that has feelings, thoughts and needs an inner touch (Dea, 2020). In its development, HR Management practices are often tied to a spiritual approach. This is because HR management has spiritual and spiritual values that are essential and innate human rights (Hidayatullah et al., 2023).

Perceived Organizational Support (POS)

Every organization/company has its own dynamics. Of course, there is social interaction that occurs in the context of the individual and the organization. Related to this, the POS concept tries to explain individual interactions with organizations that specifically study how organizations treat employees or individuals within them (Riadi, 2021a). In another point of view,

perceived organizational support (POS) can be assumed as a picture of employees' thoughts about the extent to which the company assesses the contribution and care for employee welfare based on employee perceptions. This will lead to the company's willingness and ability to appreciate employee performance that is tailored to the socio-emotional needs of employees (Putra, Okta.P, 2019).

If individuals/employees think that the organizational support they receive is high, then these employees will integrate membership as members of the organization into their self-identity and then develop a more positive influence and perception of the organization (Ariarni & Afrianty, 2017). The organizational support provided can be in the form of providing proper salaries and benefits, creating good relations between superiors and subordinates, providing adequate facilities so that created on good working conditions. Perceptions of organizational support can be measured through indicators of appreciation, superior support, working conditions, and employee welfare (Rahmayani & Wikaningrum, 2022). Therefore, organizations/companies should maintain organizational justice through monitoring and paying attention to all organizational units in order to get equal development opportunities and provide opportunities to contribute optimally according to function and adjusted (Hidayanti, 2020).

Work Engagement

Work engagement (WA) is known as a business management concept which states that employees who have high engagement are employees who are fully involved and have high work enthusiasm in their work and in matters related to long-term company activities. Thus, work engagement refers to the involvement, satisfaction, and enthusiasm of employees at work. Work engagement has developed from various concepts covering motivation, job satisfaction and organizational commitment (Riadi, 2021b).

In another view, Work engagement (WA) is considered a business management concept that stimulates individuals or employees in an organization so that they are fully involved and have high work enthusiasm in their work and in matters related to long-term company activities (Satya Cahyana & Ardi Prahara, 2020). Thus, work engagement refers to the involvement, satisfaction, and enthusiasm of employees at work. Work engagement has developed from various concepts covering motivation, job satisfaction and organizational commitment (Khusanova et al., 2021). In addition, work engagement can also be realized through the attitude and inspiration of individuals/employees such as high loyalty, willingness to work over time, employees see the company as part of the family, and employees choose to keep working at the company even though they get a better job offer (Merissa, 2018).

Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction can be viewed as a complex emotional reaction. This emotional reaction arises as a result of the encouragement, desires, demands and expectations of employees for their work which are related to the realities

felt by employees, thus causing a form of emotional reaction in the form of feelings of pleasure, feelings of satisfaction or feelings of dissatisfaction (Prosser, 2023). Job satisfaction can be influenced by several factors, namely mentally challenging work, equitable rewards, supportive working conditions, supportive colleagues (Hanifah & Rahadi, 2020).

Job satisfaction can be influenced by several factors, namely mentally challenging work, equitable rewards, supportive working conditions, supportive colleagues (Azhari et al., 2021). If the relationship between employees and the work environment has been formed in a harmonious, friendly, and mutually helpful manner, it will create a conducive working group atmosphere, which will create job satisfaction for each individual/employee. Job satisfaction has five dimensions, namely: (1) Work (2) Wages (3) Promotion opportunities (4) Promotions (5) Colleagues (K. Sivagama. S & Ms.A. Antony.S, 2020).

Conceptual Framework

This study starts from the identification of problems in the field, and is abstracted into the formulation of the problem which then takes a theoretical approach related to relevant variables. Furthermore, operationalization is carried out in one research data processing. The results of this study are to obtain empirical evidence whether or not there is an individual or simultaneous effect of the independent variables on the dependent variable. This study also compares with previous research, where:

- 1) From the research of Siska Hidayanti, et al *"Pengaruh Presepsi Dukungan Organisasi dan Keadilan Organisasi Terhadap Kepuasan Kerja Pegawai"* states that perceived organizational support partially have a positive effect on job satisfaction (Hidayanti, 2020).
- 2) From the research of Bella Merissa *"Pengaruh Work Engagement terhadap Turnover Intention melalui Job Satisfaction sebagai variable mediasi pada PT Lotte Shopping Indonesia Sidoarjo"* states that work engagement on job satisfaction at PT. Lotte Shopping Indonesia Sidoarjo is proven to have a positive and significant influence (Merissa, 2018).

By comparing previous research, this study determined the Perceived Organizational Support (POS) variable as the first independent variable (X1) and the Work Engagement variable as the second independent variable (X2). Furthermore, these two variables will be tested for their relationship with the Job satisfaction variable as the dependent variable (Y). From this description it can be formulated a flow of research ideas that encourages the rationale as follows:

Figure 2. Research Design Framework

From the research design flow above, a framework is formulated that describes the interrelationships between the variables to be developed as follows:

Figure 3. Conceptual Framework

Based on the conceptual framework above, a hypothesis test is needed to find out whether there is a relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable. The hypotheses in this study are:

1. Perceived Organizational Support is suspected of having an influence on Job Satisfaction at PT SBB OPPO. So, the hypothesis put forward is: Has the variable Perceived Organizational Support has asignificant effect on the Job Satisfaction variable.
2. Work Engagement is suspected to have an influence on Job Satisfaction at PT SBB OPPO Manufacturing. So, the hypothesis put forward is: Ha: The Work Engagement variable has a significant effect on the Job Satisfaction variable.
3. Perceived Organizational Support and Work Engagement are suspected to have an influence on Job Satisfaction at PT SBB OPPO Manufacturing. So,

the hypothesis put forward is: Ha: Perceived Organizational Support and Work Engagement have a significant effect on the Job Satisfaction variable.

METHODS

The method chosen in this study is the causal associative method which focuses on the formulation of the problem and its hypotheses. Where, a causal relationship is a causal relationship, one variable (independent) affects another variable (dependent). The research approach used is a quantitative approach. With this method and approach, it will be possible to build a view that explains predict and control a symptom (Hardani, 2020).

Variables

The variables used are the independent and dependent variables. Where from these two types of variables will be developed by forming mutually supportive attributes. Then it will be tested and conclusions will be drawn based on the interrelationships between variables (Hardani, 2020).

- 1) **Independent variable**, the independent variables in this study are Perceived Organizational Support, Work Engagement. And then, referred to as variable X1 and X2
- 2) **Dependent variable**, the dependent variable in this study is Job Satisfaction. And then, referred to as variable Y

The indicators for each variable in this study are as follows:

Table 2. Variable Indicators in Research

Research variable	Variable Operationalization Definitions	Indicators
Job Satisfaction	<i>Job Satisfaction is a positive and enjoyable emotional state. Job satisfaction reflects a person's feelings towards his work.</i>	Challenging job. Supportive working conditions. Adequate salary or wages. Personality compatibility at work.
Perceived Organizational Support	<i>Perceived Organizational support refers to employee perceptions. If the organizational support received is considered appropriate and adequate, the employee will be loyal and develop a positive influence and perception.</i>	Supportive work team. Employee welfare. convenience at work. Company response. Problems encountered. Performance Feedback.
Work Engagement	<i>a worker who has good work engagement tends to be better able to seize existing opportunities and be socially more able to develop the network he has.</i>	Vigor/spirit. Dedication. Absorption.

To measure variables, in this study using a tool in the form of a questionnaire. Where the respondents' answers will be measured using a Likert scale. The answers to each instrument have various variations from very

positive to very negative. which can be in the form of words and for the purposes of quantitative analysis, with answers in the form of a score of 1 to 5 (lowest – highest).

Population and sample

The population in this study is a generalized area consisting of objects that have certain qualities and characteristics that are determined to be studied and analyzed. In this case, the population to be studied are employees of PT SBB OPPO Manufacturing. Where population totally of 2100 people.

From the population distribution, samples will be taken. Where the method used to determine the number of samples is using the Slovin formula, by the equation as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Note: *N* is population size, *n* is sample size, *e* is error tolerance.

Where in this study the error tolerance taken is 10%, so it can be calculated as follows:

$$n = \frac{2100}{1 + 2100(0.1)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{2100}{22}$$

$$n = 95,34 \text{ round - up} = \mathbf{96}$$

Method of collecting data

To obtain data that is in accordance with the problem, the following data collection methods are used:

- 1) Primary Data Collection. Primary data is a data source that directly provides data to data collectors, by: (a) observation, this activity observes and learns directly about things that happen and are related to Perceived Organizational Support and Work Engagement on Job Satisfaction at the location of the object of study. (b) Interview. Where in this activity conducted dialogue and ask-answer. The aspects of the questions are focused on things that are reality related to perceived support, work engagement and job satisfaction. (c) Questionnaire. In this activity, respondents were given a list of questions to fill in and asked to provide opinions or answers to the questions asked. The instruments used are questionnaire forms and google forms.
- 2) Secondary Data Collection. Secondary data obtained in this study through library research with the aim of exploring material taken from books, articles, newspapers, magazines, e-news, and other sources related to the field of research being carried out.
- 3) In this study, all tests and data processing used the SPSS version 26.

Data analysis method

Validity test, to find the validity value, it is done by correlating the score of the item with the total score of the items from the variable. Test the validity

of the instrument can use the correlation formula. The correlation formula based on Pearson Product Moment is as follows:

$$r = \frac{n(\sum xy) - (\sum y)(\sum x)}{\sqrt{\{n(\sum x^2) - (\sum x)^2\}\{n(\sum y^2) - (\sum y)^2\}}} \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Note: *r* is Correlation coefficient value, *X* is independent variable, *Y* is dependent variable, *n* is number of Y and X observation pairs.

If the calculated correlation value is 0.361 then the item is declared valid, but if the correlation value is below 0.361 then the item is invalid. So that the following conditions apply:

- a) If r-count is higher than r-table, So the questionnaire items are declared valid.
- b) If r-count is lower than r-table, So the questionnaire items are declared invalid.

Reliability Test, this test was conducted to measure a questionnaire which is an indicator of the variable. A questionnaire is said to be reliable or reliable if someone's answer to the question is consistent or stable from time to time. The variable is said to be reliable if it has Cronbach's Alpha more than 0.06. To get the results of calculating the reliability coefficient, the following formula is used:

$$r_{11} = \left[\frac{k}{k-1} \right] \left[\frac{\sum \sigma_b^2}{\sigma_t^2} \right] \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

Note: *k* is number of question items, *σ_b* is number of item variances, *σ_t* is number of variances total.

Regression Analysis, this analysis is used in this study is simple regression analysis (partially) and multiple regression analysis. Simple Regression Analysis is used to determine the extent of the influence of the independent variables selected in this study on the dependent variable. Simple regression is expressed in the following equation:

$$Y' = a + bx \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

Note: *Y'* is Predicted value, *a* is Constant or if the price *X* is 0 (zero), *b* is regression Coefficient, *x* is Independent Variable Value.

Multiple regression analysis is used to determine the magnitude of the quantitative effect of a change (independent variable) on other events (dependent variable). Regression analysis using multiple regression equation formulas below:

$$Y = a + b_1 X_1 + b_2 X_2 + \dots + \epsilon \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

Note: *Y* is part sample performance, *a* is constant, *b₁, b₂* is regression coefficient, *X₁* is the 1st independent Variable, *X₂* is the 2nd independent Variable, *ε* is disturbing variable (Error).

Coefficient of determination, this test is used to measure how far the model's ability to explain the variation of the dependent variable through the

determinant value (between 0 and 1.00). If the value of R² is small, it means that the ability of the independent variables to explain the dependent variable is very limited. If the value of R² is close to 1.00, the independent variables provide almost all the information needed to predict the variation of the dependent variable. The following is the formula for calculating the coefficient of determination as follows:

$$Cd = r^2 \times 100\% \dots\dots\dots (6)$$

Where, *Cd* is coefficient of determination, *r* is correlation Coefficient.

Hypothesis test, the test is used in this study is partial test (t-test) and multiple test (f-test). The t-test is used to test as partially to show the effect of each independent variable individually on the dependent variable. To find out the results of the t-test Using the following equation:

$$t = \frac{r\sqrt{n-2}}{\sqrt{1-r^2}} \dots\dots\dots (7)$$

Note: *t* is calculated *t* value, *r* is simple correlation coefficient, *n* is number of samples. From the results of the t-test, the probability is used as the basis for deciding based on significance, thus the provisions apply:

- 1) If the significance probability is more than 0.05, then H₀ is accepted and H_a is rejected.
- 2) If the significance probability is less than 0.05, then H₀ is rejected and H_a is accepted.

In the F-test, testing the effect of the independent variables together on changes in the value of the dependent variable which can be explained by changes in the independent variables. The results of this test were traced by comparing the ANOVA to the Mean Square of the regression and the Mean Square of the residuals so that a result called F-count was obtained. To find out the results of the F-test by using the following equation:

$$F = \frac{R^2 / k}{(1 - R^2) / (n - k - 1)} \dots\dots\dots (8)$$

Note: *R* is Multiple correlation coefficient, *k* is number of independent variables, *n* is number of samples.

From the results of the F-test, the probability is used as the basis for deciding based on significance, thus the provisions apply:

- 1) If F-count > from F-table then H₀ is rejected and H_a is accepted.
- 2) If F-count < from F-table then H₀ is accepted and H_a is rejected.

RESULTS

Generally

Data analysis results in the form of a description of the general respondents. Where this elaboration aims to determine the condition and background of respondents based on gender, age, and education. The following is a tabulation in the form of the characteristics of the respondents, presented in the form of data as follows:

Table 3. Respondent Background

Respondent's Background	Background Aspect	Percentage
Gender	Male	65,70%
	Female	34,30%
Age	18-25Years	46,30%
	25-35 Years	39,70%
	> 35 Years	14%
Educational Background	Graduated High School	75%
	Graduated Diploma	10,5%
	Graduated Bachelor	14,50%

Based on the table above it is clear that most male respondents are 65,70%, and the women respondents are 34,30%. Furthermore, the dominant respondents are those who are young (18-25 years old) by 46,30% then 25-35 years by 39,70%, and others are over 35 years as 14%. Next, most of the respondents have a graduated high school of 75% some are bachelor graduates by 14,50% and some are diploma graduates by 10,50%.

Description of Research Variables

The description of the results of this study will be interpreted by describing the objective data from the results of distributing the processed questionnaires which can be seen in the following table:

Table 4. Results of the Perceived Organizational Support Questionnaire Score

Questions	Likert Scale					Total
	STS (1)	TS (2)	KS (3)	S (4)	SS (5)	
P1	0%	0%	1,0%	35,4%	63,5%	96
P2	0%	0%	24,0%	43,8%	32,3%	96
P3	0%	0%	17,7%	46,9%	35,4%	96
P4	0%	0%	10,4%	51,0%	38,5%	96
P5	0%	0%	7,3%	51,0%	41,7%	96
P6	0%	0%	9,4%	56,3%	34,4%	96
P7	0%	0%	15,6%	44,8%	39,6%	96
P8	0%	0%	28,1%	35,4%	36,5%	96
P9	0%	0%	16,7%	49,00%	34,40%	96
P10	0%	0%	12,5%	45,80%	41,70%	96
Average	0%	0%	14,2%	46,9%	39,7%	100%

According to the table above shows that Perceived Organizational Support (X1) can be seen from 96 respondents with 10 questions. Where the distribution of answers was as much as 14.2% of respondents answered Disagree (KS), as

much as 46.9% answered agreed (S), as much as 39.7% answered Strongly Agree (SS), Thus for the variable Perceived Organizational Support (X1) the majority answered "Agree (S)."

Table 5. Results of the Work Engagement Questionnaire Score

Questions	Likert Scale					Total
	STS (1)	TS (2)	KS (3)	S (4)	SS (5)	
P1	0%	0%	9,4%	40,6%	50,0%	96
P2	0%	0%	10,4%	50,0%	39,6%	96
P3	0%	0%	12,5%	50,0%	37,5%	96
P4	0%	0%	8,3%	51,0%	40,6%	96
P5	0%	0%	2,1%	55,2%	42,7%	96
P6	0%	0%	4,2%	60,4%	35,4%	96
P7	0%	0%	8,30%	41,70%	50,00%	96
P8	0%	0%	17,70%	40,60%	41,70%	96
P9	0%	0%	9,40%	55,20%	35,40%	96
P10	0%	0%	6,30%	42,70%	51,00%	96
Average	0%	0%	8,85%	48,70%	42,30%	100%

According to the table shows that Work Engagement (X2) can be seen from 96 respondents with 10 questions. As much as 8.85% answered Disagree, 48.7% answered agree, 42.3% answered Strongly Agree, and no respondents answered Strongly Disagree and Disagree. So, for the Work Engagement variable (X2) the majority answered "Agree (S)."

Table 6. Results of the Job Satisfaction Questionnaire Score

Questions	Likert Scale					Total
	STS (1)	TS (2)	KS (3)	S (4)	SS (5)	
P1	0%	0%	0%	33,30%	66,70%	96
P2	0%	1,00%	18,80%	42,70%	37,50%	96
P3	0%	0%	13,50%	45,80%	40,60%	96
P4	0%	0%	7,30%	46,90%	45,80%	96
P5	0%	0%	5,20%	47,90%	46,90%	96
P6	0%	0%	5,20%	56,30%	38,50%	96
P7	0%	0%	13,50%	44,80%	41,70%	96
P8	0%	0%	22,90%	37,50%	39,60%	96
P9	0%	0%	12,50%	49,00%	38,50%	96
P10	0%	0%	9,40%	45,80%	44,80%	96
Average	0%	0,10%	10,80%	45%	2,30%	100%

Based on the table above, it shows that Job Satisfaction (Y) can be seen from 96 respondents with 10 questions, where as many as 10.8% of respondents answered Disagree, 45% answered agree, 2.3% answered Strongly Agree, no respondents answered Strongly Disagree, and as much as 0.10% answered

Disagree. So, for the Job Satisfaction variable (Y), the majority answered "Agree (S)."

Data analysis

a. Validity test

The results of the validity test were carried out on 96 respondents so that the *df* can be calculated 96 minus 2 is 94 and alpha (α) is 0.05 obtained r-table is 0.200 the results of the validity test are as follows:

Table 7. Variant Validity Test Results
 Perceived Organizational Support

Questions	Validity test		
	r-count	r-table	Result
P1	0,452	0,2	VALID
P2	0,713	0,2	VALID
P3	0,771	0,2	VALID
P4	0,746	0,2	VALID
P5	0,743	0,2	VALID
P6	0,689	0,2	VALID
P7	0,702	0,2	VALID
P8	0,723	0,2	VALID
P9	0,711	0,2	VALID
P10	0,76	0,2	VALID

Based on the table above, it can be compared between the Pearson correlation with the r table which can be seen in the statistical table with N is 94, so the value obtained is 0.200. It can be said to be valid because r-count is higher than r-table, therefore all questionnaire statements are valid.

Table 8. Variant Validity Test Results Work
 Engagement

Questions	Validity test		
	r-count	r-table	Result
P1	0,457	0,2	VALID
P2	0,676	0,2	VALID
P3	0,724	0,2	VALID
P4	0,738	0,2	VALID
P5	0,656	0,2	VALID
P6	0,763	0,2	VALID
P7	0,656	0,2	VALID
P8	0,744	0,2	VALID
P9	0,719	0,2	VALID
P10	0,558	0,2	VALID

Based on the table above, it can be compared between the Pearson correlation with the r table which can be seen in the statistical table with N is 94, so the value obtained is 0.200. overall, result of r-count is higher than r-

table, therefore all questionnaire statements are valid because the Pearson correlation values are all above the r-table value of 0.200. So, the results of the X2 validity test above the results can be said to be valid.

Table 9. Variant Validity Test Results
Job satisfaction

Questions	Validity test		
	r-count	r-table	Result
P1	0,439	0,2	VALID
P2	0,552	0,2	VALID
P3	0,621	0,2	VALID
P4	0,543	0,2	VALID
P5	0,655	0,2	VALID
P6	0,672	0,2	VALID
P7	0,584	0,2	VALID
P8	0,592	0,2	VALID
P9	0,566	0,2	VALID
P10	0,64	0,2	VALID

Based on the table above it can be compared between the Pearson correlation with the r table which can be seen in the statistics table with N is 94, the value obtained is 0.200. It can be said to be valid because r-count is greater than r-table, then from the results of the Y validity test above the results can be said to be valid, so further tests can be carried out.

b. Reliability test

In this study, the Cronbach Alpha formula was used because the questionnaire used in this study did not have answers that were wrong or zero. The test results obtained are as follows:

Table 10. Variable Perceived
Organizational Support Reliability
Test Results

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
0,886	10

Based on the table above, each variable has a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.886, the value is higher than 0.60. So, it can be concluded that the results from the table above regarding the variable Perceived Organizational Support (X1) are proven to be reliable.

Table 11. Variable Work Engagement Reliability Test Results

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
0,861	10

Based on the table above, each variable has a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.861, the value is more than 0.60. So, it can be concluded that the Work Engagement variable (X2) is proven to be reliable.

Table 12. Variable Job Satisfaction Reliability Test Results

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
0,785	10

Based on the table above, each variable has a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.785, the value is more than 0.60 with a total of ten statements. So, it can be concluded that the results from the table above regarding the Job Satisfaction variable (Y) are proven to be reliable and the respondents show stability and had high consistency in answering all questionnaires.

c. Regression Analysis

- 1) Simple regression analysis (partially). In the simple regression analysis, tests were carried out on the Perceived Organizational Support variable on the Job Satisfaction variable, and the Work Engagement variable on Job Satisfaction separately. In order to know the influence between these variables. Here is, the calculation results are as follows:

Table 13. Simple Regression Test Results Perceived Organizational Support on Job Satisfaction

Model	Coefficients^a				t	Sig.
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients			
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
(Constant)	12,116	1,458		8,311	0	
1 Perceived Organizational Support	0,733	0,034	0,912	21,525	0	

a. Dependent Variable: Jobs Satisfaction

From the table above, the regression equation can be made as follows:

$$Y' = 12, 116 + 0, 733 X_1 \dots\dots\dots (9)$$

According to the equation above, the coefficient for Perceived Organizational Support (X1) competence is 0.733 with a constant of 12.116. The closer to number 1, the stronger the effect. Thus, from the regression equation model can be interpreted that that if there is an increase of one point, then Job Satisfaction (Y) will increase by 0.733.

Table 14. Simple Regression Test Results Work Engagement on Job Satisfaction

coefficients ^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	11,038	2,346		4,705	0
1 Work Engagement	0,744	0,054	0,819	13,817	0

a. Dependent Variable: Jobs Satisfaction

From the table above, the regression equation can be made as follows:

$$Y' = 11,038 + 0,744 X_2 \dots\dots\dots (10)$$

According to the equation above, the coefficient for Work Engagement (X2) competence is 0.744 with a constant of 12.116. The closer to number 1, the stronger the effect. Thus, from the regression equation model can be interpreted that if there is an increase of one point, then Job Satisfaction (Y) will increase by 0.733.

- 2) Multiple regression analysis. In multiple regression analysis, tests were held on the variables Perceived Organizational Support and Work Engagement on the Job Satisfaction variables as simultaneous. In order to know the influence between the independent variable and the dependent variable. Here is, the calculation results are as follows:

Table 15. Results of Multiple Regression Tests Perceived Organizational Support and Work Engagement on Job Satisfaction

coefficients ^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	8,104	1,506		5,38	0
1 Perceived Organizational Support	0,551	0,046	0,685	11,887	0
Work Engagement	0,271	0,052	0,298	5,174	0

a. Dependent Variable: Jobs Satisfaction

From the table above, the regression equation can be made as follows:

$$Y = 8,104 + 0,551X_1 + 0,271X_2 \dots\dots\dots (11)$$

According to the results of the analysis above, the coefficient for Perceived Organizational Support (X1) competence is 0.551 with a constant of 8.104, and the coefficient for Work Engagement (X2) is 0.271. Its means that if there is an increase of one point in the variable Perceived Organizational Support (X1), then Job Satisfaction (Y) will increase by 0.551 and if there is an increase in Work Engagement (X2) by one point, Job Satisfaction (Y) will increase by 0.271.

d. Coefficient of determination

In Coefficient of determination, tests were held on the variables Perceived Organizational Support and Work Engagement on the Job Satisfaction variables as simultaneous. In order to know the magnitude of the contribution of the influence of the independent variables on the independent variables. Here is, the calculation results are as follows:

Table 16. Results Test of the Coefficient of Determination X1 on Y

Model Summary^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.912 ^a	0,831	0,83	1,579

a. Predictors: (Constant), Perceived Organizational Support
 b. Dependent Variable: Jobs Satisfaction

Table 17. Results Test of the Coefficient of Determination X2 on Y

Model Summary^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.819 ^a	0,67	0,667	2,209

a. Predictors: (Constant), Work Engagement
 b. Dependent Variable: Jobs Satisfaction

Table 18. Results Test of the Coefficient of Determination X1 and X2 on Y

Model Summary^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.932 ^a	0,869	0,866	1,399

a. Predictors: (Constant), Work Engagement, Perceived Organizational Support
 b. Dependent Variable: Jobs Satisfaction

Based on the table above, the R square value at X1 is 0.831. So, the magnitude of the influence of Perceived Organizational Support (X1) on Job Satisfaction (Y) is 83.1%, the remaining 16.9% is influenced by other variables outside the variables not discussed. The value of R square Work Engagement (X2) is 0.670. So, the magnitude of the influence of Work Engagement (X2) on Job Satisfaction (Y) is 67.0%, the remaining 33% is influenced by other variables outside the variables not discussed. Meanwhile, the simultaneous R

square value is 0.869. So, the magnitude of the influence of Perceived Organizational Support (X1) and Work Engagement (X2) on Job Satisfaction (Y) is 86.9%, the remaining 13.1% is influenced by other variables outside the variables not discussed in this study.

e. Hypothesis test

- 1) **t-test.** In the test, t test is carried out by comparing the calculated t value to the t table and the probability index between variables. From the results of the partial t test, the following results were obtained:

Table 19. Results of the t-test Perceived Organizational Support (X1) on Job Satisfaction (Y)

Coefficients^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	12,116	1,458		8,311	0
1 Perceived Organizational Support	0,733	0,034	0,912	21,525	0

a. Dependent Variable: Jobs Satisfaction

Table 20. Results of the t-test Work Engagement (X2) on Job Satisfaction (Y)

Coefficients^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	11,038	2,346		4,705	0
1 Work Engagement	0,744	0,054	0,819	13,82	0

a. Dependent Variable: Jobs Satisfaction

Based on the table above, the t-count value for Perceived Organizational Support is 21,525 and it is known that the t-table is 1.985 with a significant level of 0.000 up to 0.05. Because t-count is higher than t-table, H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, its means that there is a significant influence between Perceived Organizational Support on Job Satisfaction. while the calculated t-count for works engagement (X2) is 13.817. Because t-count is higher than t-table, H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, its means that there is a positive and significant influence between Work Engagement (X2) on Job Satisfaction (Y).

- 2) **F-test.** In the test, F-test is carried out by comparing the calculated t-count to the t-table of independent variables as simultaneous and the probability index on dependent variable. From the results of the partial t test, the following results were obtained:

Table 21. Results of the *F*-test Perceived Organizational Support (X1) and Work Engagement (X2) on Job Satisfaction (Y)

ANOVA ^a					
Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	1208,177	2	604,089	308,577	.000 ^b
1 Residual	182,062	93	1,958		
Total	1390,24	95			

a. Dependent Variable: Jobs Satisfaction

b. Predictors: (Constant), Work Engagement, Perceived Organizational Support

Based on the table above, the *F*-count value is 308.577 and the *F*-table value is 3.09. Because the *F*-count is higher than *F*-table with a significant level of 0.000 up to 0.05. Its shows that *H*₁ and *H*₂ are accepted. Its means that there is an Influence of Perceived Organizational Support and Work Engagement together on Job Satisfaction.

DISCUSSION

- 1) Discussion of the results of the Perceived Organizational Support (X1) and Job Satisfaction (Y) tests, where the influence between Perceived Organizational Support (X1) and Job Satisfaction (Y) is based on the coefficient of determination (R) of 83.1%, the calculation of the hypothesis *t* is sig 0.000 up to 0.05 and *t*-count is higher than *t*-table (21,525 and 1,985), it's shows that X1 (Perceived Organizational Support) has a positive and significant effect on Y (Job Satisfaction). The research results are in line with the research conducted by Siska Hidayanti (Hidayanti, 2020).

Related to the work environment at PT SBB OPPO Manufacturing, it's possible because there are thoughts of most individuals/employees who think that high Job Satisfaction from employees in the company is strongly influenced by organizational support on a social scale as well as within the organization itself. Job satisfaction is expected in the form of providing support to employees at work to improve employee welfare. The form of organizational support is to contribute to employees, so that employees feel satisfied with their work, organizational support can change the attitudes and behaviour of employees so that they continue to contribute optimally to the company.

- 2) Discussion of the results of the Work Engagement (X2) and Job Satisfaction (Y) tests, where the influence between Work Engagement (X2) and Job Satisfaction (Y) based on the coefficient of determination (R) of 67.0%, the calculation of the hypothesis is sig 0.000 up to 0.05, and *t*-count is higher than *t*-table (13.817 and 1.985). It's shows that X2 (Work Engagement) has a positive and significant effect on Y (Job Satisfaction). The research results are in line with the research conducted by Bella Merissa (Merissa, 2018).

Related to the work environment at PT SBB OPPO Manufacturing, this possible to individuals/employees to have hope that the resources

owned by the company (Job Resources) and individual resources (Personal Resources) interact with the company's relate to workload (Job Demands). When the resources provided by the company and the resources owned by individuals are sufficient to overcome the workload, it will lead to employee job satisfaction.

- 3) Discussion of the results of the Perceived Organizational Support (X1) and the Work Engagement (X2) are simultaneous on Job Satisfaction (Y) tests, where influence between Perceived Organizational Support (X1) and Work Engagement (X2) on Job Satisfaction (Y). which the coefficient of determination (R) of 86.9%, the calculation of the F hypothesis is sig 0.000 up to 0.05 F-count is higher than F-table (308.577 and 3.09), it's shows that Perceived Organizational Support (X1) and Work Engagement (X2) as simultaneous have a positive effect and jointly significant on Job Satisfaction. This research is in line with the research of Siska Hidayanti (Hidayanti, 2020). Where, Siska Hidayanti noted that F-count was obtained with a value of 21.528 while F-table was obtained with a value of 3.11. so that she proves that there is a significant influence between the variables Perceived Organizational Support and Work Engagement on job satisfaction.

Related to the work environment at PT SBB OPPO Manufacturing, it's supposed that with perceived organizational support it is considered capable of creating job satisfaction, and with work engagement that meets expectations it also forms job satisfaction. This allows the emergence of further expectations from individuals/employees, in which it is hoped that the company will be able to fulfil the right perceived organizational support and facilitate the formation of adequate work engagement so that employee job satisfaction will arise while at the same time forming a feeling of happiness and loyalty to the organization/company.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions

Based on the formulation of the problem and the results of the analysis described, the following conclusions follow as: Perceived Organizational Support (X1) has a positive and significant influence on Job Satisfaction (Y). this is evidenced by the calculation of the t test, where the value of t-count is higher than t-table (21,525 up to 1.985), and a sig value of 0.000 up to 0.05. It's means that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. So, there is a positive and significant influence Perceived Organizational Support (X1) Job Satisfaction (Y).

Work Engagement (X2) has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction (Y). This is evidenced by the results of the t test, with t-count is higher than t-table (13.817 and 1.985), and a sig value of 0.000 up to 0.05. Thus, H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. It's means that there is a significant influence between the variable Work Engagement (X2) on Job Satisfaction (Y).

Perceived Organizational Support (X1) and Work Engagement (X2) simultaneously have a positive and significant influence on Job Satisfaction (Y). This is evidenced in the results of calculating F-count is higher than F-table

(308.577 and 3.09), and a significance value of 0.000 up to 0.05. It's means that H1 and H2 are accepted, it's concluded that Perceived Organizational Support (X1) and Work Engagement (X2) together have a significant effect on Job Satisfaction (Y).

Recommendations

By paying attention to the positive and strong relationship between Perceived Organizational Support and work engagement on Job Satisfaction at PT SBB OPPO Manufacturing. So, it is expected that the company always strives to provide support to its employees, increase employee commitment and pay attention to employee needs by providing satisfaction at work by implementing several relevant human resource strategies.

In order to create positive work dynamics, especially related to the implementation of Work Engagement, the company should make a clear set of SOPs and Job Desks as well as create punishment and reward packages for employees. Besides that, it is necessary to involve all groups in the work environment to mutually maintain a conducive work environment to form a sense of comfort at work.

FURTHER STUDY

For future researchers, it is suggested to develop this study by examining other factors that can influence Perceived Organizational Support and Work Engagement on company Job Satisfaction, such as organizational commitment and leadership variables. It is recommended for future researchers to process research with methods and approaches other than quantitative. so that the information obtained can be more valid and easier in data processing.

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